

A ternary MWCNT/Ceria/Polyaniline composite for corrosion protection

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays, researchers try to replace the classical application of Cr⁶⁺ by other environmentally friendly method. Among them, the use of lanthanide ions such as Ce³⁺ is a new strategy. Our aim was to investigate the combination of MWCNT, ceria and polyaniline as pigments for the corrosion protection. The facile preparation of MWCNT/Ce/polyaniline nanocomposites will be reported. The electrostatic interactions between carboxylate groups of MWCNT and Ce³⁺ ions directs the growth of ceria nanoparticles at the surface of MWCNT. Ce(III) will be formed on the surface of o-MWCNT and thermal treatment under oxidizing conditions is expected to promote Ce(III) oxidation into Ce (IV). TEM images showed that ceria nanoparticles of diameter 10 nm decorated the walls of MWCNTs in the MWCNT/Ce/PANI composites. These ternary composites were dispersed as pigments in polyvinyl butyral matrix to study their anticorrosive performance. The corrosion protection efficiency was tested in neutral saline conditions (immersion in 3.5 wt % NaCl solution and salt spray exposure).

1 INTRODUCTION

Metallic corrosion is a global problem with a substantial economic impact [1]. In addition, corrosion can lead to catastrophic failures of airplanes, bridges, cars... Therefore, it is important to protect metals from corroding. Chromate (Cr) coatings provide an excellent protection against corrosion. However, the widely used Cr compounds have been banned in Europe since 2007 and soon worldwide due to their highly carcinogenic effect [2,3]. Driven by regulations, researchers have focused towards the development of green alternative coatings [4]. Lanthanide ions, such as Ce³⁺, ytterbium Y³⁺, lanthanum La³⁺, praseodymium Pr³⁺, neodymium Nd³⁺ are among new strategies to replace the chromium(VI) [5,6]. They have been identified as environmentally friendly alternatives to chromate conversion coatings [7]. In addition, lanthanides are economically competitive products, since some of them in particular cerium are relatively abundant in nature [8,9]. Recently, there is an increased interest in potential applications of cerium oxide in corrosion protection of metals [10]. Sharmila et al. demonstrated that cerium oxide shows good performance as a corrosion inhibitor for steel in hydrochloric acid (HCl) and sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄) solution media [11]. Wang et al. reported that the golden-yellow-colored cerium conversion coatings, obtained by cerium salt immersion in ethanol solution and post-treated in 3 wt.% sodium phosphate Na₃PO₄ aqueous solution, significantly reduced the corrosion rate of AZ91D magnesium alloy in NaCl solution [12].

The use of conductive polymers (CPs) for the corrosion protection of metals has received substantial attention over the last three decades. The emeraldine form of polyaniline has been the most thoroughly investigated CP. Emeraldine polyaniline occurs in two forms: doped (salt) and dedoped (base). The structures of these two forms are shown in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1. Chemical conversion between the emeraldine base and emeraldine salt.

Common mechanisms of corrosion protection are interpreted as physical barrier, adsorption, anodic protection and shift of electrochemical interface [13-16].

On the other hand, carbon nanotubes (CNTs) and inorganic nanoparticles have attracted much attention owing to their unique properties and a wide range of applications in catalysis, sensing and energy storage. In the composite, CNT can serve as a high-performance support because of their large surface area, exceptional electrical properties, mechanical stability and unique hollow tubular backbone structures. Nanoparticles can be uniformly dispersed on the sidewalls of CNT and have electronic charge transfer with CNT in either covalent or noncovalent interactions [17,18]. As a result, the composites of nanoparticles (NP) and MWCNT can provide NP-based materials with significantly improved performance.

Based on these findings, we have decided to incorporate the unique properties of MWCNT, PANI and cerium together by preparing MWCNT/Ce/PANI ternary composites as new anticorrosive pigments.

The study has been entirely carried out using low carbon steel panels coated with a bottom layer of polyvinyl butyral resin (PVB) incorporating 2 wt% cerium-based composites as a pigment and a PVB top-coat. Our aim was to examine the efficiency of ceria based coatings for corrosion protection of steel. The corrosion protection efficiency was tested in neutral saline conditions (immersion in 3.5 wt % NaCl solution).

2 EXPERIMENTAL PART

Aniline (99.5 %) and ammonium peroxydisulfate (APS) (>98 %) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and used as received. $\text{Ce}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was from Acros Organics. MWCNT were purchased from Bayer society. All experiments were carried out with distilled water. The oxidized MWCNT (o-MWCNT) was obtained by the following method: 0.1 g of MWCNT was added in a mixture of concentrated nitric acid (10 mL) and sulfuric acid (30 mL). The suspension was ultrasonicated over 10 h and then 100 mL of distilled water was added into the mixture. It was centrifuged, washed with distilled water until the dispersion turned neutral and finally dried at 50 °C under vacuum over night.

2.1 Synthesis of MWCNT/Ce(III,IV) composites

20 mg of pristine MWCNT (p-MWCNT) was dispersed in 50 mL of distilled water by ultrasonic irradiation for 20 min. Then 1.05 g of $\text{Ce}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was added to the reaction mixture drop by drop. After vigorous stirring for 1h, a 5 mg/ml NaOH solution was added slowly into the above-mixed solution until a pH value of 9 was reached. The reaction mixture was then centrifuged, washed with distilled water (100 ml) and dried under vacuum at 50 °C for 24h. The same protocol was applied for o-MWCNT to obtain o-MWCNT/Ce(III).

p-MWCNT/Ce(IV) was obtained from p-MWCNT/Ce(III) by calcination in air at 450 °C for 20 min. The same protocol was applied for o-MWCNT to obtain o-MWCNT/Ce(IV). For comparison, CeO₂ NPs were also prepared by the same process except for the absence of CNT.

2.2 Synthesis of MWCNT/Ce(III,IV)/PANI ternary composites

120 mg of (p-, o-) MWCNT/Ce(III) nanotubes was dispersed in 50 mL of distilled water by ultrasonic treatment for 20 min. In a typical procedure, 588 µl of aniline followed by 1.84 g of APS were added to the solution. After 1h stirring, the precipitate was filtrated, washed with distilled water and acetone and dried under vacuum at 30°C for 24h. The ES form of PANI in MWCNT/Ce(IV)/ES was converted to the emeraldine base (EB) form of PANI by treatment with 0.1 M NH₄OH for 24 h to give MWCNT/Ce(IV)/EB.

2.3 Preparation of protective films

3 g of polyvinyl butyral (PVB) (Sigma-Aldrich, with M.W. 60,000) was dissolved in 20 mL of ethanol with continuous stirring for 24 hours. Then, the 60 mg of Ce based pigment (MWNT/Ce(III), MWNT/Ce(III)/ES, MWNT/Ce(IV)/ES, MWNT/Ce(IV)/EB) was dispersed in 3mL of ethanol by the aid of sonication for 20 min and the resulting suspension was added to PVB solution and stirred for 1 hour. The pigment content in PVB was 2 wt.%. Low carbon steel panels of 12,5x7,5x0,3 cm³ were sand-blasted, degreased with refluxing acetone and dried. Then, a first layer of the prepared dispersion was bar cast onto the cleaned steel substrate. After drying at room temperature for 24 h, a topcoat layer of PVB was applied over the bottom layer. The thickness of the coating was measured using a micrometer screw gauge (Elcometer 456/3). Panels with a coating thickness of 40±2 µm were selected for corrosion study.

2.4 Characterization

Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) measurements were performed on a Zeiss Supra 40 VP Field Emission equipped with an energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) probe (Oxford X-max-20). SEM samples were mounted on aluminum studs using double-sided carbon tape and were then coated with gold to improve conductivity. One drop of MWCNT (5mg) dispersion in 10 mL of ethanol was deposited on the carbon tape to observe pristine and o-MWCNT. Samples for EDS analysis were in the form of pellets.

Transmission electron microscope (TEM) JEOL JEM 2000 FX was used to assess the morphology. X-ray diffraction patterns (DRX) were acquired with a Ni-filtered Cu K radiation source ($\lambda=0.154$ nm) using a Siemens[®] D5000 X-ray diffractometer. The Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) technique was employed to study the protection performance of the PVB coatings on steel during immersion in 3.5% solution of NaCl. EIS was conducted using a 273A potentiostat (EGG/PAR) coupled to a Solartron 1255 frequency response analyser. EIS measurements were carried out at the open circuit potential with a 10 mV rms amplitude perturbation over the frequency range 20 mHz–100 kHz. A conventional three-electrode cell was used. It is composed of a platinum foil as auxiliary electrode, a saturated calomel reference electrode (SCE) and the coated metal as working electrode [19].

A Varian Spectra AA-800 atomic absorption spectrometer was used to determine the amount of iron in the NaCl solution after 10 days corrosion test.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Characterization of o-MWCNT

The characterization of the MWCNT after the acid treatment was the first step of our study. Entangled MWCNT were clearly seen in the case of pristine MWCNT in Fig.1A. After oxidation with

strong oxidants such as nitric acid and sulfuric acid (Fig. 1B), some bundles appeared exfoliated and curled.

Treatment of MWCNT with strong acids (nitric and sulfonic acid) assisted with ultrasonic lead to a severe etching of the graphitic surfaces, so shorter tubes are obtained [20]. The average lengths of pristine and oxidized MWCNT obtained from SEM images are about 1.1 μm and 0.7 μm , respectively (Fig. 2). Therefore, the length of MWCNTs is not severely reduced with acid oxidation. The absolute values of the zeta potential for p-MWCNT (-20 mV/-30 mV) were lower than the values for o-MWCNT (-40 mV/-50 mV) over a wide pH range (3-9) which is due to the acidic groups which were present on o-MWCNT.

Figure 1. SEM images of A – pristine MWCNT and B – oxidized MWCNT.

Figure 2. Length distributions of pristine MWCNT and oxidized MWCNT.

3.2 Preparation of MWCNT/Ce(III, IV)/PANI composites

The preparation process of MWNT/Ce NPS/PANI nanotubes was carried out in two steps. First, MWCNTs were coated with ceria NPs to give MWCNT/ceria binary composites. Then,

MWCNT/ceria were coated with a PANI layer by in situ polymerization of aniline and ternary composites were formed.

The direct evidence of the formation of MWCNT/Ce(III,IV) composites was given by SEM images, which showed a rough surface while the surface of MWCNT is smooth (Fig. 3).

o-MWCNT was uniformly coated with cerium oxide nanoparticles whereas for MWCNT/Ce(III,IV) composites prepared from p-MWCNT, the distribution of Ce(III) nanoparticles is inhomogeneous : some Ce(III) particles were deposited on the surface of MWCNT but a large amount of MWCNT are still naked.

Figure 3. SEM images of binary composites MWCNT/Ce(III): A– oxidized MWCNT; B – pristine MWCNT.

The presence of cerium was verified by EDS analysis and it is found that the amount of cerium in o-MWCNT/Ce composites is greater than that in p-MWCNT/Ce composites (Fig. 4). To our opinion, the enhanced amount of cerium deposited on the walls of o-MWCNT is related to the large amount of acidic groups, mainly carboxylic acid on their surface which promotes the adsorption of cerium cations and helps to better disperse the CNTs [22].

Figure 4. EDS spectra for o-MWCNT/Ce(III).

SEM and TEM (Fig.5) images of the samples show that the thermal treatment at 450°C did not induce significant changes in the morphology of MWCNT/Ce composites.

Figure 5. SEM and TEM images respectively of binary composites MWCNT/Ce(IV): A,B – oxidized MWCNT; C,D – pristine MWCNT.

The crystalline structure of the samples was further examined by X-ray Diffraction (XRD) analysis. The XRD patterns of MWNT/Ce(III) and MWNT/Ce(IV) samples show diffraction peaks at $2\theta = 30, 33, 47.5$ and 56.3° which agree with the JCPDS file for CeO_2 (JCPDS 34-394) in a cubic fluorite structure [23]. It is to be noted that the diffraction peaks corresponding to crystalline ceria were much more intense for the thermally treated sample which suggests that the thermal treatment promotes the oxidation of Ce(III) species and that it increases the crystallinity.

SEM images of ternary MWCNT /Ce(III,IV)/PANI show that a tubular layer of a uniform PANI layer is present on the MWCNT surface (Fig. 6). The average diameter of MWCNT/Ce(III)/PANI was around 55-70 nm for pristine MWCNT and oxidized MWCNT. From the average diameter of the MWCNT/Ce(II) binary composite of 50-55 nm, the average thickness of PANI layer is around 2.5-7.5 nm

Figure 6. SEM images of ternary composites MWCNT/Ce(III): A– oxidized MWCNT; B – pristine MWCNT.

EDS spectra of MWCNT/Ce(III,IV)/PANI showed the presence of N, S and Ce elements (Fig.7). This confirms the formation of a polyaniline layer onto the surface of MWCNT/Ce (III). The presence of sulfur element suggests that polyaniline is in the emeraldine salt form and that it is doped by hydrogensulfate (and/or sulfate) anions originated from the APS reduction.

Figure 7. EDS spectra for MWCNT/Ce(III)/PANI composites.

3.3 Corrosion study

MWCNT/Ce(III), MWCNT/Ce(III)/ES, MWCNT/Ce(IV)/ES and MWCNT/Ce(IV)/EB pigments were incorporated with PVB and deposited on low carbon steel panels. Bode diagrams for the different coatings as a function of exposure time in 3.5 % NaCl solution are presented in Fig. 8.

Figure 8. Bode plots for the neat PVB, PVB coatings loaded with binary and ternary composites after different immersion times in 3.5% NaCl solution.

The low frequency impedance modulus represents the global resistance of the system ($|Z|_{0.02\text{Hz}} \sim R_s + R_p + R_{ct}$ with R_s , the electrolyte resistance, R_p , the pore resistance and R_{ct} the charge-transfer resistance) and is thus a useful parameter to characterize the protective properties of a coating [57,58,59]. In the initial period of immersion (1h), the value of $|Z|_{0.02\text{Hz}}$ for PVB was around $10^6 \Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$. After 3 days of immersion, the value of $|Z|_{0.02\text{Hz}}$ gradually decreased to $10^5 \Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$ until the end of the immersion. Fig. 8 shows that MWCNT/Ce and MWCNT/Ce/PANI pigments enhanced the corrosion protection of steel. Initially, there was approximately three orders of magnitude difference for the value of $|Z|_{0.02\text{Hz}}$ for MWCNT/Ce(IV)/ES and EB compared with PVB. Both MWCNT/Ce(IV)/ES and MWCNT/Ce(IV)/EB showed relatively good protection properties during the initial hours of immersion, with LF impedance values near $10^9 \Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$ whereas the initial $|Z|_{0.02\text{Hz}}$ for PVB was found to be near $10^6 \Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$. For the binary MWCNT/Ce(III) coating, the value of $|Z|_{0.02\text{Hz}}$ was slightly decreased from 10^8 to $10^6 \Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$ after 22 days. The value of $|Z|_{0.02\text{Hz}}$ of MWCNT/Ce(III)/ES coating was around $10^7 \Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$ initially, then it decreased quickly to $10^5 \Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$ after 22 days of immersion, ie to the LF impedance value found with PVB. Nevertheless, the values of $|Z|_{0.02\text{Hz}}$ for the coatings loaded with MWCNT/Ce(III) and with MWCNT/Ce(IV)/EB were found to be one and two orders of magnitude higher than PVB, respectively.

Corrosion process was also monitored by measuring the concentration of the iron ions released after exposure to salt-water containing 3.5 wt% of NaCl for 10 days (Table 1). The results showed that the corrosion activity was strongly suppressed in PVB coatings loaded with MWCNT/Ce(III)/EB pigments.

Table 1. Iron concentration after 10 days immersion test in 3.5% NaCl solution.

Samples	Fer concentration (mg/L)
PVB	1.2
MWCNT/Ce(III)	0.4
MWCNT/Ce(IV)/ES	0.25
MWCNT/Ce(III)/ES	0.15
MWCNT/Ce(IV)/EB	0.05

The present results suggest that PANI in the EB form is more efficient than PANI in the ES form to protect metal from corrosion. However, we suspect that these results must not be generalized and could be related to the poor barrier properties of the ES form compared to the EB form of PANI.

4 CONCLUSION

In conclusion, binary MWCNT/Ce and ternary MWCNT/Ce/PANI composites were synthesized. TEM images showed that ceria nanoparticles of diameter 10 nm decorated the walls of MWCNTs in the MWCNT/Ce/PANI composites. The corrosion study showed that the PVB film loaded with MWCNT/Ce(IV)/EB resulted in the best corrosion protection performance in neutral saline conditions (immersion in 3.5% NaCl solution). The excellent corrosion protection performance of MWCNT/Ce(IV)/EB is due to the combined effect of ceria NPs and PANI in the EB form. The mechanism of protection of steel by composite fillers combining two active components, such as Cerium oxide NPs and PANI is complex and experimental work must be pursued in order to ascertain mechanism synergetic effect between all components of the anticorrosive pigment.

REFERENCES

- [1] O'Connor, P. D. T. Corrosion and corrosion control, (3rd edn). *Quality and Reliability Engineering International*, **1**, 1985, pp. 271.
- [2] Zheludkevich, M. L.; Shchukin, D. G.; Yasakau, K. A.; Möhwald, H.; Ferreira, M. G. S. Anticorrosion Coatings with Self-Healing Effect Based on Nanocontainers Impregnated with Corrosion Inhibitor. *Chemistry of Materials*, **19**, 2007, pp. 402-411.
- [3] Shchukin, D. G.; Zheludkevich, M.; Yasakau, K.; Lamaka, S.; Ferreira, M. G. S.; Möhwald, H. Layer-by-Layer Assembled Nanocontainers for Self-Healing Corrosion Protection. *Advanced Materials*, **18**, 2006, pp. 1672-1678.
- [4] Rosero-Navarro, N. C.; Paussa, L.; Andreatta, F.; Castro, Y.; Durán, A.; Aparicio, M.; Fedrizzi, L. Optimization of hybrid sol-gel coatings by combination of layers with complementary properties for corrosion protection of AA2024. *Progress in Organic Coatings*, **69**, 2010, pp. 167-174.
- [5] Zandi Zand, R.; Verbeken, K.; Adriaens, A. Corrosion resistance performance of cerium doped silica sol-gel coatings on 304L stainless steel. *Progress in Organic Coatings*, **75**, 2012, pp. 463-473.
- [6] Mora, N.; Cano, E.; Polo, J. L.; Puente, J. M.; Bastidas, J. M. Corrosion protection properties of cerium layers formed on tinplate. *Corrosion Science*, **46**, 2004, pp. 563-578.
- [7] Joshi, S.; Fahrenholtz, W. G.; O'Keefe, M. J. Alkaline activation of Al 7075-T6 for deposition of cerium-based conversion coatings. *Surface and Coatings Technology*, **205**, 2011, pp. 4312-4319.
- [8] Tavandashti, N. P.; Sanjabi, S. Corrosion study of hybrid sol-gel coatings containing boehmite nanoparticles loaded with cerium nitrate corrosion inhibitor. *Progress in Organic Coatings*, **69**, 2010, pp. 384-391.

- [9] Nazeri, A.; Trzaskoma-Paulette, P. P.; Bauer, D. Synthesis and Properties of Cerium and Titanium Oxide Thin Coatings for Corrosion Protection of 304 Stainless Steel. *Journal of Sol-Gel Science and Technology*, **10**, 1997, pp. 317-331.
- [10] Patil, S.; Kuiry, S. C.; Seal, S. Nanocrystalline ceria imparts better high-temperature protection. *Proc R Soc A*, **460**, 2004, pp. 3569-3587.
- [11] Sharmila, R.; Selvakumar, N.; Jeyasubramanian, K. Evaluation of corrosion inhibition in mild steel using cerium oxide nanoparticles. *Materials Letters*, **91**, 2013, pp. 78-80.
- [12] Wang, C.; Zhu, S.; Jiang, F.; Wang, F. Cerium conversion coatings for AZ91D magnesium alloy in ethanol solution and its corrosion resistance. *Corrosion Science*, **51**, 2009, pp. 2916-2923.
- [13] Schauer, T.; Joos, A.; Dulog, L.; Eisenbach, C. D. Protection of iron against corrosion with polyaniline primers. *Progress in Organic Coatings*, **33**, 1998, pp. 20-27.
- [14] Wessling, B.; Posdorfer, J. Corrosion prevention with an organic metal (polyaniline): corrosion test results. *Electrochimica Acta*, **44**, 1999, pp. 2139-2147.
- [15] Wessling, B. Corrosion prevention with an organic metal (polyaniline): Surface ennobling, passivation, corrosion test results. *Materials and Corrosion*, **47**, 1996, pp. 439-445.
- [16] Sathiyarayanan, S.; Karpakam, V.; Kamaraj, K.; Muthukrishnan, S.; Venkatachari, G. Sulphonate doped polyaniline containing coatings for corrosion protection of iron. *Surface and Coatings Technology*, **204**, 2010, pp. 1426-1431.
- [17] Haremza, J. M.; Hahn, M. A.; Krauss, T. D.; Chen, S.; Calcines, J. Attachment of Single CdSe Nanocrystals to Individual Single-Walled Carbon Nanotubes. *Nano Letters*, **11**, 2002, pp. 1253-1258.
- [18] Robel, I.; Bunker, B. A.; Kamat, P. V. Single-Walled Carbon Nanotube-CdS Nanocomposites as Light-Harvesting Assemblies: Photoinduced Charge-Transfer Interactions. *Advanced Materials*, **17**, 2005, pp. 2458-2463.
- [19] Zhang, D.; Shi, L.; Fu, H.; Fang, J. Ultrasonic-assisted preparation of carbon nanotube/cerium oxide composites. *Carbon*, **44**, 2006, pp. 2853-2855.
- [20] Datsyuk, V.; Kalyva, M.; Papagelis, K.; Parthenios, J.; Tasis, D.; Siokou, A.; Kallitsis, I.; Galiotis, C. Chemical oxidation of multiwalled carbon nanotubes. *Carbon*, **46**, 2008, pp. 833-840.
- [21] Fahrenholtz, W. G.; O'Keefe, M. J.; Zhou, H.; Grant, J. T. Characterization of cerium-based conversion coatings for corrosion protection of aluminum alloys. *Surface and Coatings Technology*, **155**, 2002, pp. 208-213.
- [22] Zhang, D.; Fu, H.; Shi, L.; Fang, J.; Li, Q. Carbon nanotube assisted synthesis of CeO₂ nanotubes. *Journal of Solid State Chemistry*, **180**, 2007, pp. 654-660.
- [23] Suresh, R.; Ponnuswamy, V.; Mariappan, R. Consequence of source material on the surface properties of nebulizer spray coated cerium oxide thin films. *Vacuum* **109**, 2014, pp. 94-101.